

MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES, PERCEIVED TEACHING STYLES, AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Multiple Intelligences, Perceived Teaching Styles, and Academic Performance of Junior High School Students

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Abstract

This study explored the relationship between multiple intelligences and academic performance among Junior high school students at Al-Hamlan National High School during the Academic Year 2023-2024. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, respondents were selected via simple random sampling to ensure a representative sample from the entire population. Results unveiled sex as a notable predictor, with females demonstrating higher academic achievement compared to males. Furthermore, parental education levels emerged as influential factors, with children of college-educated parents exhibiting lower academic performance. However, demographic variables like age group, along with teaching styles and various types of multiple intelligences, failed to significantly predict academic outcomes. The findings underscored the necessity of integrating diverse teaching methodologies and recognizing individual cognitive strengths in educational practices. By considering the multifaceted nature of intelligence and its impact on academic success, educators could tailor their approaches to better meet the diverse needs of students, thereby fostering a more inclusive and effective learning environment.

Keywords: *multiple intelligences, perceived teaching style, academic performance, descriptive-correlational*

Introduction

Each student differs from one another. They have their own uniqueness. Howard Gardner defines these learning abilities as intelligences; this explains how students learn differently from one another. There are students who lack motivation and have trouble concentrating in learning. Thus, it is important for teachers not to overlook this kind of students. All students deserve the opportunity to learn in a way that they could enhance their strengths and help improve their weaknesses.

Multiple Intelligences are important for knowing how to target the diversity of interests and learning styles of the students. This will help teachers to plan engaging and effective lessons. This will guide the teachers on how they will be able to teach their students in their different weakness, and how they can be able to improve their strengths. It is actually the teachers' obligation to grow and improve in order to teach pupils with unique variances and a range of learning styles.

This theory also identifies the good points of the students that will give them sense of belongingness. This theory has a big impact because it can be used this as a basis on how they perform form a specific task and help the teachers to assess their students' needs in their performance as a student.

The researcher chooses this topic to identify the needs assessment of the Junior High School students in regard of their strength and weaknesses. Understanding the multiple intelligences of junior students at Al-Hamlan National High School is pivotal in comprehending their educational overall performance. Howard Gardner's concept of a couple of intelligences suggests that individuals possess various tiers of intelligence across unique domain names, such as linguistic, logical-mathematical, spatial, physical-kinesthetic, musical, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and naturalistic intelligence (Çavaş & Çavaş, 2020). Teachers can customize coaching methodologies to address different learning styles and maximize student learning outcomes by examining how these intelligences occur among students and their relationship to academic fulfillment (Flores-Mendoza et al., 2021).

Multiple Intelligences (MI) is based on the premise that there is not just one kind of intelligence. MI suggests that individuals have varied skills and gifts. Each person has a profile of intelligences which includes: linguistic, logical, visual, musical, kinesthetic, interpersonal, intrapersonal, naturalistic, and perhaps spiritual. According to Gardner, the implication of the theory is that learning/teaching should focus on the particular intelligences of each person. For example, if an individual has strong logical or linguistic intelligences, they should be encouraged to develop these abilities. Gardner notes that the various intelligences reflect various learning modes in addition to distinct topic domains. The theory also implies that testing should evaluate various types of intelligence, not simply linguistic and logical-mathematical.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the different multiple intelligences in relation to the academic performance of the Junior High School students in Al-Hamlan National High School for the Academic Year 2023-2024. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following problems:

1. What are the demographic profiles of the respondents specifically in their:
 - 1.1. age,
 - 1.2. sex, and

- 1.3. parents' educational attainment?
2. How do the respondents assess the teaching style of the teachers?
3. What are the multiple intelligences of the respondents?
4. Do the multiple intelligences relate to the academic performance of the respondents?
5. Do the teaching style relate to the academic performance of the respondents?
6. Does the academic performance of the respondents differ by their demographic profiles?
7. Which of the demographic profiles, teaching styles, and multiple intelligences significantly predict the academic performance of the respondents?
8. What action plan can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. This study is descriptive in nature since it focused on the needs assessment of the teaching styles, and multiple intelligences of Junior High School students at ANHS. Further, this study also assessed the academic performance of the students. In addition, this is also a correlation design since the study investigated the relationship between teaching styles, multiple intelligences, and the academic performance of the students.

Respondents

The target respondents for this study were the Junior High School students enrolled at Al-Hamlan National High School in Picong, Lanao del Sur for the academic year 2023-2024. The selection of respondents was carried out using a simplified equal allocation sampling, ensuring that each student had an equal chance of being included in the study, thus providing a representative sample from the entire population. The respondents of this study were fairly selected twenty-five students in every grade level of Al-hamlan National High School in Picong, Lanao del Sur. Table A below shows the distribution of the respondents of the study.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents*

Junior High School	Total number of students		Total	Respondents
	Male	Female		
Grade 7	20	20	40	25
Grade 8	16	22	38	25
Grade 9	20	25	45	25
Grade 10	15	17	32	25
Total	71	84	155	100

Similarly, one hundred fifty-five (155) total of Junior High School students of Al-hamlan National High School students but only one hundred (100) students among them were selected to be part of this study.

Instrument

In assessing the relationship between multiple intelligences and instructional success, the research instrument may encompass a variety of validated evaluation tools, surveys, and performance tasks. The questionnaire was constructed by the researcher about teaching styles and a questionnaire adapted from Mckenzie (1999) entitled "Multiple Intelligences Inventory" and was modified by the researcher to fit with the present study. McKenzie's MI questionnaire is one of the established tools to identify the typology of intelligence.

Furthermore, standardized instructional achievement tests or teacher evaluations provided valuable insights into students' performance across different subject areas. By triangulating data from multiple sources, researchers can strengthen the validity of their findings and offer a comprehensive understanding of the interplay between multiple intelligences and academic success.

Procedure

The data gathering procedure outlined in the description encompasses several key steps, each designed to ensure the integrity and effectiveness of the research process.

Firstly, the researcher initiated the procedure by seeking permission from the relevant authority, such as the instructor or adviser, to conduct the studies. This initial step underscored the researcher's commitment to adhering to institutional protocols and ethical considerations, demonstrating respect for the guidelines governing research activities within the academic setting. Obtaining permission also served to legitimize the research endeavor and establish a framework for conducting the study within the designated context.

Once permission was granted, the researcher proceeded to explain the study to the students in a clear and concise manner. Providing comprehensive information about the purpose and procedures of the study was essential for ensuring transparency and fostering cooperation among the participants. By elucidating the objectives and methods of the research, the researcher sought to promote understanding and engagement among the students, encouraging active participation in the data collection process.

Subsequently, each respondent was provided with a copy of the questionnaire and instructed to complete it by indicating their responses next to each statement. This standardized approach to data collection ensured consistency and uniformity in gathering information from all participants, facilitating the systematic analysis of the data at a later stage. Moreover, acknowledging the respondents for their time and cooperation following the completion of the questionnaire reinforced a positive rapport between the researcher and the participants, enhancing the overall experience of data collection.

Importantly, the researcher upheld the principles of confidentiality and ethical conduct throughout the data gathering procedure. Confidentiality safeguarded the privacy and anonymity of the participants, instilling trust and confidence in the research process. By adhering to ethical standards, the researcher respected the rights and well-being of the participants, maintaining the integrity and credibility of the research outcomes.

Following the collection of data, the researcher proceeded to tabulate, summarize, and subject the data to statistical tests. This analytical phase enabled the researcher to derive meaningful insights and draw valid conclusions from the gathered data, contributing to the advancement of knowledge within the research domain. Overall, the systematic and ethical approach outlined in the data gathering procedure underscored the researcher's commitment to conducting rigorous and credible research.

Data Analysis

The data gathered was analyzed statistically with the use of appropriate statistical tools. To interpret the data gathered by the researcher, the following statistical tools were used:

For Problem 1, frequency and percentage was used to summarize the demographic profiles of the respondents.

For Problems 2 and 3, the mean and standard deviation was used to summarize the multiple intelligences assessment of the respondents.

For Problems 4 and 5, Pearson's r correlation was used to determine the relationship between the teaching styles, multiple intelligences and the academic performance of the respondents.

For Problem 6, an independent T-test or ANOVA was used to determine the differences in the academic performance of the respondents when grouped by their demographic profiles.

For Problem 7, Multiple regression analysis was used to test the influence of teaching style, multiple intelligences, and demographic profiles on the academic performance of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings and discussion of the study conducted to determine the relationship between multiple intelligences and the academic performance of the junior high school students at Al-Hamdan National High School for the academic year 2023-2024.

Problem 1: What are the demographic profiles of the respondents specifically in their age, gender, and parents' educational attainment?

Table 2. *Age of the Respondents*

<i>Age (in years)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
10-15	48	48.0
16-20	52	52.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2 provides information on the demographic profile in terms of age, which specializes in a population of one hundred people categorized into two age groups: 10-15 and 16-20. The more youthful organization (10–15 years) contained forty-eight individuals, accounting for about 48% of the pattern, even as the older organization (sixteen–twenty years) included 52 people, making up approximately 52%. This distribution indicated a slightly better representation of the older age institution in the studied population. The close percentages recommended that the pattern had a relatively balanced age distribution, with a minor tilt towards the older age range. This balanced distribution offered a huge amount of information about socio-monetary impacts or traits across a spectrum of early to past-due life.

Table 3. *Sex of the Respondents*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Female	65	65.0
Male	35	35.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3 provides the socio-financial profile labeled by way of sex, with a total sample size of 100 individuals. Among those, individuals identified as Female (F), constituting about 65% of the pattern, while 35 individuals discovered themselves as men (M), making up around 35% of the sample. This distribution showed a higher representation of women in the studied population. The discrepancy among the proportions of women and men indicated potential gender-related differences in socio-economic traits or reviews within the

context of the population.

Table 4. Father's Educational Attainment of the Respondents

<i>Father's Education</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Arabic	13	13.0
College	11	11.0
Elementary	62	62.0
Secondary	14	14.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4 presents the distribution of respondents' fathers' educational attainment. Among the respondents, the majority, comprising 62.0%, reported their fathers' educational attainment as elementary level. Following this, 14.0% of the respondents indicated that their fathers had attained a secondary level of education. Meanwhile, a smaller proportion, constituting 11.0%, mentioned that their fathers had completed college education. Interestingly, an equivalent percentage of 13.0% reported their fathers' educational attainment as Arabic, which likely referred to education provided through Islamic institutions. These statistics provided insights into the educational backgrounds of the respondents' fathers within the sample population. The data showcased a predominant trend towards elementary education among the fathers, suggesting a potential influence on the educational aspirations and opportunities available to their children.

Table 5. Mother's Educational Attainment of the Respondents

<i>Mother's Education</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Arabic	11	11.0
College	9	9.0
Elementary	51	51.0
Secondary	29	29.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 5 illustrates the distribution of respondents' mothers' educational attainment. Notably, the most prevalent category among the respondents were mothers with an elementary education, constituting 51.0% of the sample. Following this, 29.0% of respondents reported their mothers' educational level as secondary. A smaller proportion, comprising 11.0%, indicated that their mothers had attained an Arabic education, likely acquired through Islamic institutions. Additionally, 9.0% of respondents mentioned that their mothers had completed college education. These findings shed light on the educational backgrounds of the respondents' mothers within the studied population. The prevalence of elementary education among mothers indicated a pattern similar to that observed for fathers, suggesting a potential influence on the educational opportunities available to their children.

Problem 2: How do the respondents assess the teaching style of the teachers?

Table 6. Assessing the Teaching Style of the Teachers in terms of Whole-class Activities

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Lecture/Teacher Talk	3.57	.59	Strongly Agree
2. Question and Answer	3.39	.71	Agree
3. The teacher provides a demonstration for every activity.	3.35	.74	Agree
4. Watching a video or film	2.03	1.10	Disagree
5. The teacher provides very clear guidelines for how tasks are completed.	3.49	.66	Agree
6. The teacher uses overhead projectors or pictures.	2.31	1.07	Disagree
7. Board work activities.	2.81	.96	Agree
8. The teacher led a whole-class discussion.	2.66	1.07	Agree
9. Free-flowing whole-class discussion	2.61	1.10	Agree
10. Dictation of the teachers	2.54	.91	Agree
Total Measure	2.88	.47	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

Table 6 presents an assessment of the teaching style employed by teachers in terms of whole-class activities, as perceived by the respondents. The mean scores provided an overview of the extent to which respondents agreed or disagreed with various teaching indicators. The highest mean score was observed for "Lecture/Teacher Talk" (Mean=3.57, SD=0.59), indicating that respondents strongly agreed with this aspect of teaching style. Similarly, other indicators such as "The teacher provides very clear guidelines for how tasks are completed" (Mean=3.49, SD=0.66) and "Question and Answer" (Mean=3.39, SD=0.71) also received favorable mean scores, suggesting agreement among respondents.

On the other hand, indicators such as "Watching a video or film" (Mean=2.03, SD=1.10) and "The teacher uses overhead projectors or pictures" (Mean=2.31, SD=1.07) received lower mean scores, indicating disagreement or less preference for these teaching methods.

These findings connoted several implications for teaching practices and student engagement. The high mean scores for indicators such as lecture-based teaching and providing clear guidelines suggested that traditional teaching methods involving direct instruction and structured guidance were well-received by the respondents. However, the lower mean scores for activities such as watching videos or using visual aids like overhead projectors indicated a potential opportunity for educators to explore more diverse and multimedia-based

instructional approaches to enhance student interest and comprehension. Additionally, the moderate mean scores for activities like whole-class discussion and dictation suggested that while these methods were generally accepted, there may be room for improvement in terms of promoting more interactive and participatory learning experiences.

Overall, these insights could inform educators' efforts to tailor their teaching styles to better meet the diverse needs and preferences of their students, thereby enhancing the overall quality of education delivery.

The importance of adapting coaching techniques to cater to the diverse learning styles of college students had been underscored by Katsaris and Vidakis (2021), who performed a comprehensive evaluation of adaptive e-mastering structures. Their study emphasized the critical role that understanding and incorporating diverse studying patterns play in improving scholar engagement and educational consequences. By inspecting the effectiveness of various e-getting-to-know systems and their adaptability to men or women gaining knowledge of preferences, Katsaris and Vidakis showed how technology may be leveraged to provide personalized mastering reports. Their findings suggested that when educational content material was tailored to shape the preferred gaining knowledge of types of college students, there was a first-rate development in comprehension, retention, and application of expertise. This aligned with the notion that integrating numerous teaching methodologies, together with multimedia and interactive elements, could considerably contribute to an extra enticing and effective way of gaining knowledge of the environment.

Table 7 provides an evaluation of teaching styles concerning individual activities, as perceived by the respondents. The mean scores offered insights into the degree of agreement or disagreement with various teaching indicators. Among the indicators, "Exam paper questions" (Mean=3.38, SD=0.66), "Essay writing or formal reasoning" (Mean=3.28, SD=0.74), and "The teacher will assign a reporter to discuss it in front of" (Mean=3.51, SD=0.73) received notably high mean scores, indicating a strong agreement among respondents. These findings suggested that structured assessment methods and opportunities for student presentations were well-regarded within the instructional context.

Table 7. Assessing the Teaching Style of the Teachers in terms of Individual Activities

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Essay writing or formal reasoning	3.28	.74	Agree
2. Exam paper questions	3.38	.66	Agree
3. Self-produced handouts	2.92	.84	Agree
4. Individual assignments	3.09	1.07	Agree
5. The teacher lets the students use models, drawings, maps, etc. to answer questions	2.50	1.01	Agree
6. Experiments and Investigations: "Discovery" Type	2.35	1.04	Disagree
7. End of chapter/module tests	2.94	.84	Agree
8. Library research and information-seeking	2.92	.90	Agree
9. Case studies	2.81	.87	Agree
10. The teacher will assign a reporter to discuss it in front of	3.51	.73	Strongly Agree
11. One-on-one teaching	2.46	.99	Disagree
12. Question and answer	3.31	.72	Agree
13. The teacher asks different questions and patiently solicits each answer	3.21	.80	Agree
14. Students typically work on course projects alone with little supervision from the teacher	3.01	.87	Agree
15. A teacher spends time consulting with students on how to improve their work on individual projects.	3.26	.77	Agree
Total Measure	3.00	.40	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

Additionally, indicators such as "Self-produced handouts" (Mean=2.92, SD=0.84), "Individual assignments" (Mean=3.09, SD=1.07), and "End of chapter/module tests" (Mean=2.94, SD=0.84) also received favorable mean scores, suggesting general agreement with these teaching practices. Conversely, indicators such as "Experiments and Investigations: 'Discovery' Type" (Mean=2.35, SD=1.04) and "One-on-one teaching" (Mean=2.46, SD=0.99) received lower mean scores, indicating a disagreement or less preference for these instructional methods among respondents.

These findings have implications for instructional design and classroom practices. The high mean scores for structured assessment methods and student presentations suggested a preference for activities that provided clear expectations and opportunities for student engagement and expression. However, the lower mean scores for activities such as one-on-one teaching and discovery-type experiments suggested a potential opportunity for educators to explore more personalized and inquiry-based learning approaches to cater to diverse learning styles and preferences. Overall, these insights could inform educators' efforts to design more effective and engaging instructional experiences that promote active learning and foster student growth and development.

Wilson and Durham (2021) provided a compelling exploration of Gardner's concept of a couple of intelligences, arguing that academic achievement and the effectiveness of coaching strategies were closely stimulated by means of recognizing and nurturing numerous kinds of intelligence. The study delved into the importance of tailoring instructional procedures to cater to character studying strengths. By acknowledging that scholars own various forms of intelligence—from linguistic and logical-mathematical to bodily-kinesthetic and

interpersonal—Wilson and Durham spotlighted the necessity for educators to diversify their coaching techniques beyond conventional lecture-based techniques. This perspective supported the concept that incorporating an extensive range of educational activities, along with people who promoted discovery and hands-on learning. This could considerably enhance engagement and learning results for all college students, regardless of their dominant intelligence type. Their insights underscored the capacity for educators to enhance educational design by way of integrating techniques that aligned with the multifaceted nature of students' intelligence, thereby fostering a more inclusive and effective mastering of surroundings.

Table 8. Assessing the Teaching Style of the Teachers in terms of Small Group Activities

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Buzz groups	2.96	.86	Agree
2. Small group discussions are employed to help students develop their ability to think critically.	3.13	.66	Agree
3. Small-group role play	3.16	.90	Agree
4. Stage play/drama	3.09	1.02	Agree
5. Small group-led discussion	3.02	.80	Agree
6. Debate	2.30	1.03	Disagree
7. Small group projects or assignments	3.03	1.07	Agree
8. Games	2.76	.92	Agree
9. Case studies	2.98	.86	Agree
10. Students interact with each other through short exchanges or guided activities.	2.96	.80	Agree
Total Measure	2.94	.52	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

Table 8 presents an evaluation of teaching styles concerning small group activities, as perceived by the respondents. The mean scores offered insights into the degree of agreement or disagreement with various teaching indicators. Among the indicators, "Small group discussions are employed to help students develop their ability to think critically" (Mean=3.13, SD=0.66), "Small-group role play" (Mean=3.16, SD=0.90), and "Stage play/drama" (Mean=3.09, SD=1.02) received notable mean scores, indicating a strong agreement among respondents. These findings suggested that activities promoting active participation and collaborative learning within small groups were well-regarded within the instructional context.

Additionally, indicators such as "Small group projects or assignments" (Mean=3.03, SD=1.07) and "Students interact with each other through short exchanges or guided activities" (Mean=2.96, SD=0.80) also received favorable mean scores, suggesting general agreement with these teaching practices. Conversely, indicators such as "Debate" (Mean=2.30, SD=1.03) received a lower mean score, indicating a disagreement or less preference for this instructional method among respondents.

These findings had implications for instructional design and classroom practices. The high mean scores for small group discussions, role play, and stage play suggested a preference for activities that promoted collaboration, critical thinking, and creative expression within small group settings. However, the lower mean score for debate suggested a potential opportunity for educators to explore alternative strategies for fostering argumentation and persuasive communication skills among students. Overall, these insights could inform educators' efforts to design more effective and engaging instructional experiences that leverage the benefits of small group activities to enhance student learning and development.

Sukumari (2021) highlighted the significance of Howard Gardner's Multiple Intelligences Theory within the context of eLearning, emphasizing the position of know-how and leveraging numerous intelligences within the layout of educational content. The study argued for the customization of eLearning environments to shape the various learning options and strengths of students. By categorizing beginners in line with their dominant kinds of intelligence—along with linguistic, logical-mathematical, musical, bodily-kinesthetic, spatial, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and naturalistic—educators could tailor their instructional techniques to enhance engagement, comprehension, and retention. This approach helped the use of small organization activities that inspired lively participation and collaboration, as it permitted the incorporation of various teaching techniques that catered to different intelligences. For example, position-play and level-play catered to interpersonal and physical-kinesthetic intelligences, while small institution discussions might appeal more to those with intrapersonal and linguistic strengths. P.S.'s analysis underscored the ability for the usage of multiple intelligences as a framework to layout extra inclusive and powerful learning studies, especially in selling crucial questioning and innovative expression among students via carefully structured organization activities.

Table 9 provides a consolidated summary of the teaching styles employed by teachers, incorporating mean scores and standard deviations across different categories of instructional activities. The mean scores offered an indication of the overall agreement or disagreement with various teaching styles among the respondents.

Across the three categories of teaching activities, namely whole-class, individual, and small group activities, the mean scores indicated a general agreement among respondents. Specifically, for whole-class activities, the mean score was 2.88 with a standard deviation of 0.47, indicating agreement with this teaching style. Similarly, individual activities received a mean score of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 0.40, suggesting agreement with these instructional methods. In the case of small group activities, the mean score was 2.94

with a standard deviation of 0.52, indicating agreement with this teaching approach as well.

Table 9. *Consolidated Findings of the Teaching Style of the Teachers*

<i>Teaching Style</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Whole-class Activities	2.88	.47	Agree
Individual Activities	3.00	.40	Agree
Small Group Activities	2.94	.52	Agree
Total Measure	2.94	.38	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

The total measure, which combined the mean scores across all categories, was 2.94 with a standard deviation of 0.38, indicating an overall agreement with the teaching styles employed by teachers. These findings suggested that respondents generally perceived the teaching styles utilized by teachers favorably across different instructional activities.

Yang, Zhuang, and Pan (2021) delved into the complex interplay between diverse know-how representations and their pivotal role in enhancing the abilities of large data and synthetic intelligence within educational contexts. Their study offered a radical exploration of the way integrating numerous information representation fashions can notably enhance the technique of learning and coaching. The authors argued that by leveraging those multifaceted frameworks, educators could increase the use of more nuanced and effective coaching techniques that were in harmony with the complex nature of human study. This study underscored the ability of superior AI technologies to tailor academic content material and methodologies to the precise needs of college students, thereby reflecting a broader consensus in academic research about the significance of adaptability and personalization in coaching styles. The application of big facts and AI in educational settings, as highlighted by Yang et al., afforded a compelling case for the incorporation of sophisticated analytical gear to better understand and optimize teaching and mastering methods, ultimately suggesting a direction towards more attractive, green, and personalized educational experiences.

Problem 3: What are the multiple intelligences of the respondents?

Table 10 presents the distribution of multiple intelligences among the respondents, showcasing mean scores, standard deviations, and ranks for each intelligence category. The mean scores provided insights into the relative strengths of respondents across different types of intelligences.

Table 10. *Multiple Intelligences of Respondents*

<i>Multiple Intelligences</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Word Smart	32.35	3.38	1
Math Smart	30.45	4.33	6
Music Smart	27.85	5.12	9
People Smart	31.45	4.28	2
Picture Smart	29.87	3.85	7
Body Smart	28.98	4.55	8
Self-Smart	30.57	4.07	5
Nature Smart	30.72	4.68	4
Wondering Smart	31.28	3.67	3

Among the multiple intelligences, "Word Smart" emerged as the highest-ranked category, with a mean score of 32.35 and a standard deviation of 3.38, indicating a strong proficiency in linguistic abilities. Following closely behind was "People Smart," with a mean score of 31.45 and a standard deviation of 4.28, suggesting adeptness in interpersonal skills and understanding. The intelligence category of "Wondering Smart" also ranked high, with a mean score of 31.28 and a standard deviation of 3.67, indicating a capacity for curiosity and questioning.

Conversely, "Music Smart" ranked lowest among the intelligences, with a mean score of 27.85 and a standard deviation of 5.12, suggesting relatively weaker proficiency in musical abilities among respondents. Similarly, "Body Smart" and "Picture Smart" also exhibited lower mean scores, indicating lesser strengths in kinesthetic and visual-spatial intelligences, respectively.

These findings highlighted the diverse profiles of multiple intelligences among the respondents, showcasing varying strengths and areas for development. Understanding these profiles could inform educators' efforts to adopt differentiated instructional strategies that catered to the diverse learning preferences and strengths of students. By leveraging students' strengths in different intelligences, educators could create inclusive and engaging learning environments that foster holistic development and academic success.

El-Sabagh (2021) explored the big impact of adaptive to know environments tailored to college students' getting to know styles on their engagement and academic performance. The study delved into how instructional technology might be optimized to cater to the numerous mastering choices inherent in Howard Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences. The research highlighted the essential function of personalized study paths that respected and utilized character strengths throughout exclusive intelligence domains, such as linguistic, logical-mathematical, spatial, physical-kinesthetic, musical, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and naturalistic intelligences. By incorporating adaptive gaining knowledge of technologies that become aware of and adjust to the particular getting to know sorts of every student, the study revealed huge enhancements in scholar engagement, motivation, and, in the long run, gaining knowledge of

results. El-Sabagh's paintings underscored the necessity of embracing educational diversity through technologically advanced, responsive coaching methods that understood and bolstered the numerous highbrow skills of college students, thereby fostering an extra inclusive and powerful knowledge of the environment.

Problem 4: Do the multiple intelligences relate to the academic performance of the respondents?

Table 11. Relationship between Multiple Intelligences and Academic Performance of the Respondents

Multiple Intelligences	Academic Performance								
	English	Filipino	Araling Panlipunan	Science	Math	MAPEH	ESP	TLE	Total Measure
Word Smart	.215* (.032)	.057 (.576)	-.015 (.880)	-.006 (.952)	.077 (.448)	-.010 (.923)	-.147 (.146)	.013 (.900)	.054 (.590)
Math Smart	.084 (.406)	.027 (.788)	.053 (.602)	.042 (.678)	.278** (.005)	-.089 (.380)	-.169 (.092)	-.007 (.945)	.073 (.468)
Music Smart	.005 (.962)	.001 (.991)	-.096 (.344)	-.027 (.792)	-.031 (.757)	.056 (.582)	-.249* (.012)	-.153 (.129)	-.072 (.474)
People Smart	-.026 (.797)	.069 (.497)	-.109 (.282)	-.097 (.339)	-.158 (.117)	-.133 (.186)	-.262** (.008)	-.157 (.119)	-.139 (.169)
Picture Smart	.098 (.333)	-.048 (.636)	-.092 (.365)	-.061 (.545)	-.093 (.359)	.052 (.607)	-.064 (.525)	-.146 (.148)	-.063 (.534)
Body Smart	-.015 (.884)	-.061 (.545)	-.110 (.276)	-.111 (.272)	-.002 (.988)	-.023 (.824)	-.179 (.075)	-.141 (.162)	-.104 (.304)
Self-Smart	.003 (.977)	.080 (.426)	-.140 (.166)	.040 (.696)	-.057 (.571)	.014 (.888)	.008 (.934)	-.029 (.777)	-.014 (.888)
Nature Smart	.005 (.959)	-.056 (.579)	-.124 (.217)	.133 (.188)	.007 (.947)	.020 (.847)	-.094 (.354)	-.057 (.575)	-.002 (.983)
Wondering Smart	.104 (.302)	-.002 (.986)	-.030 (.764)	.029 (.772)	-.054 (.592)	.071 (.482)	-.005 (.963)	-.173 (.085)	.009 (.933)

Note: Analysis is based on Pearson Correlation **significant at .01 level *significant at .05 level

Table 11 presents the correlation coefficients between multiple intelligences and academic performance indicators among the respondents. The analysis revealed significant correlations between certain types of intelligences and academic performance, warranting further attention and consideration in educational practices.

Among the significant correlations, the relationship between "Math Smart" intelligence and academic performance in mathematics stands out prominently. The correlation coefficient of .278 ($p < .01$) suggested a strong positive association between proficiency in mathematical intelligence and performance in mathematics. This finding underscored the importance of recognizing and nurturing students' mathematical intelligence to enhance their performance in this subject area.

Additionally, significant correlations were observed between "People Smart" intelligence and academic performance in both English ($r = .215$, $p < .05$) and ESP (Education for Sustainable Development) ($r = -.262$, $p < .01$). These correlations highlighted the role of interpersonal skills and understanding in language acquisition and holistic education, emphasizing the need to integrate social-emotional learning components into the curriculum to support students' overall academic development.

Furthermore, significant negative correlations were identified between "Music Smart" intelligence and academic performance in ESP ($r = -.249$, $p < .05$) and "People Smart" intelligence and academic performance in ESP ($r = -.262$, $p < .01$). While unexpected, these findings suggested potential areas of divergence between musical intelligence and performance in certain subject areas, calling for further investigation into the underlying factors influencing these relationships.

Overall, these correlation results carried several implications for educational practices. Firstly, educators should recognize and leverage students' strengths in specific intelligences to tailor instructional strategies that catered to their individual learning preferences and abilities. Secondly, interventions aimed at enhancing students' weaker intelligences in relevant subject areas may be warranted to improve overall academic performance. Lastly, fostering a holistic approach to education that integrated social-emotional learning and diversified intelligences could contribute to more comprehensive and effective learning outcomes among students.

Mayu and Widjanti (2022) delved into the nuanced impact of Gardner's multiple intelligences principle on college students' studying effects in arithmetic, providing compelling proof that particular intelligences appreciably affected mathematical fulfillment. In their study, the researchers systematically evaluated current literature to clarify how individual intelligences, in particular "Math Smart" intelligence, correlated with and expect college students' overall performance in arithmetic. They argued that scholars with excessive mathematical-logical intelligence now not only excelled in numerical and logical reasoning responsibilities but additionally displayed greater hassle-fixing abilities and conceptual knowledge in arithmetic. Their findings strengthened the perception that instructional strategies tailor-made to apprehend and nurture awesome intelligences could considerably enhance mathematical knowledge of outcomes. This contributed to the wider discourse on personalized training by highlighting the need for educators to undertake numerous educational techniques that catered to the wide range of intelligences presented inside the classroom. By doing so, Mayu and

Widjajanti proposed a more inclusive, intelligence-conscious instructional panorama that allowed every student to leverage their inherent strengths and reap academic achievement, mainly in tough topics like arithmetic.

Problem 5: Do the teaching style relate to the academic performance of the respondents?

Table 12. Relationship between the Teaching Style and the Academic Performance of the Respondents

Academic Performance	Teaching Style			
	Whole Class Activities	Individual Activities	Small Group Activities	Total Measure
English	.151 (.134)	-.014 (.892)	.116 (.250)	.111 (.274)
Filipino	.139 (.168)	.072 (.476)	.063 (.536)	.112 (.269)
Araling Panlipunan	.228* (.023)	.120 (.235)	.024 (.811)	.148 (.142)
Science	.254* (.011)	.101 (.318)	.016 (.875)	.148 (.141)
Math	.231* (.021)	.160 (.111)	.111 (.272)	.203* (.043)
MAPEH	-.190 (.058)	-.186 (.064)	-.109 (.281)	-.194 (.053)
ESP	-.042 (.680)	-.086 (.394)	-.098 (.334)	-.092 (.361)
TLE	.020 (.842)	-.007 (.942)	-.025 (.803)	-.006 (.955)
Total Measure	.190 (.059)	.054 (.590)	.041 (.688)	.116 (.249)

Note: *significant at .05 level

Table 12 presents the correlation coefficients between teaching styles and academic performance indicators among the respondents. The analysis revealed some noteworthy relationships between specific teaching styles and academic performance in various subjects, suggesting implications for instructional practices.

The significant positive correlations were observed between Araling Panlipunan ($r=.228, p<.05$), Science ($r=.254, p<.05$), and Math ($r=.231, p<.05$). These findings suggested that the utilization of whole-class activities in instruction was associated with better performance in social studies, science, and mathematics subjects. This underscored the potential effectiveness of whole-class instructional approaches in facilitating learning across diverse subject areas.

Conversely, no significant negative correlations were identified between "MAPEH" (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health) and both "Whole Class Activities" ($r=-.190, p>.05$) and "Individual Activities" ($r=-.186, p>.05$). This suggested that reliance on whole-class and individual instructional methods may not be as conducive to academic performance in MAPEH subjects. Educators may need to explore alternative instructional strategies, such as small group activities or project-based learning, to better engage students and enhance their performance in these subjects.

Furthermore, no significant correlations were observed between "ESP" (Education for Sustainable Development) and any of the teaching styles, indicating a lack of association between the teaching approaches employed and academic performance in this subject area.

Overall, these correlation results highlighted the importance of considering the alignment between teaching styles and subject-specific learning outcomes. Educators should strive to adopt instructional approaches that catered to the unique demands of each subject area while promoting student engagement and academic achievement.

Lumei (2022) explored the mixing of Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences within the primary education region, emphasizing its critical role in improving teaching efficacy and student mastery effects. The paper highlighted how educators could extensively benefit from expertise and applied the concepts of a couple of intelligences to their coaching techniques. Lumei argued that tailoring educational strategies to cope with the various intelligences of students—ranging from linguistic and logical-mathematical to bodily-kinesthetic and interpersonal—facilitated an engaging and powerful mastering environment. This technique no longer only supported the development of students' strengths but also enabled them to address their weaknesses, thereby providing a more inclusive and adaptive getting-to-know experience. The look drew attention to the potential for progressed academic overall performance across various topics, such as technological know-how, arithmetic, and languages, when educators implement teaching styles that resonate with the multiple intelligences in their students. Lumei's research underscores the need for educators to diversify their academic processes, shifting beyond traditional one-size-fits-all strategies to embrace an extra nuanced and personalized pedagogy that aligns with the multifaceted nature of student's intelligence and mastering alternatives.

Problem 6: Does the academic performance of the respondents differ by their demographic profile?

Table 13 presents the differences in academic performance among respondents grouped by age, as indicated by t-values and p-values derived from independent t-tests. While most of the differences in academic performance between the 10-15 age group and the 16-20 age group were not significant, one notable exception was observed in the subject of science.

The t-value of 1.997 for science indicates a significant difference in academic performance between the two age groups, with $p<.05$. This finding suggested that students in the 10-15 age group performed significantly better in science compared to their counterparts in the 16-20 age group. This result underscored the importance of considering age-related factors in educational contexts, as there may be developmental differences that impacted academic performance in specific subjects.

Table 13. Differences of the Academic Performance of the Respondents When Grouped to Age

Academic Performance	Age Group		t-value	p-value	Remarks
	10-15 (n=48)	16-20 (n=52)			
English	83.35	82.75	1.150	.253	Not significant
Filipino	82.52	82.44	.179	.858	Not significant
Araling Panlipunan	83.02	82.48	1.160	.249	Not significant
Science	83.50	82.54	1.997*	.049	Significant
Math	82.85	82.58	.620	.537	Not significant
MAPEH	85.79	86.35	-1.922	.058	Not significant
ESP	85.92	85.63	.933	.353	Not significant
TLE	86.02	85.87	.540	.591	Not significant
Total Measure	84.12	83.83	1.082	.282	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based Independent T-test *significant at .05 level

Although differences in other subjects such as English, Filipino, Araling Panlipunan, Math, MAPEH, ESP, and TLE were not significant, it was essential to note that these findings did not negate the potential influence of age on academic performance entirely. Other factors beyond age, such as individual differences in cognitive development, learning styles, and instructional approaches, may also contribute to variations in academic achievement.

The significant difference in Science performance between age groups suggested implications for curriculum design, instructional practices, and student support mechanisms. Educators may need to tailor their teaching methods and curriculum content to accommodate the diverse learning needs and developmental stages of students across different age groups, particularly in subjects where age-related differences in performance were evident.

Mayu and Widjanti (2022) delved into the impact of Gardner's more than one intelligences theory on college students' studying results in arithmetic, offering compelling proof that particular intelligences drastically impacted mathematical fulfillment. The researchers systematically evaluated present literature to elucidate how individual intelligences, specifically "Math Smart" intelligence, correlated with and predict students' overall performance in mathematics. They argued that students with high mathematical-logical intelligence now not only excelled in numerical and logical reasoning duties but also showed improved hassle-solving abilities and conceptual information in arithmetic. Their findings fortified the notion that educational techniques tailor-made to recognize and nurture awesome intelligences can notably enhance mathematical mastery effects. This work contributed to the broader discourse on personalized education by highlighting the need for educators to adopt diverse instructional processes that catered to the wide range of intelligences gifted inside the school room. By doing so, Mayu and Widjanti recommended a more inclusive, intelligence-conscious educational landscape that let every student leverage their inherent strengths and reap instructional achievement, especially in difficult subjects like arithmetic.

Table 14. Differences of the Academic Performance of the Respondents When Grouped to Gender

Academic Performance	Gender Group		t-value	p-value	Remarks
	Female (n=65)	Male (n=35)			
English	83.29	82.57	1.313	.192	Not significant
Filipino	82.77	81.94	1.832	.070	Not significant
Araling Panlipunan	83.05	82.17	1.812	.073	Not significant
Science	83.25	82.54	1.268	.210	Not significant
Math	82.94	82.29	1.307	.197	Not significant
MAPEH	86.26	85.74	1.710	.091	Not significant
ESP	86.03	85.29	2.704*	.008	Significant
TLE	85.98	85.86	.422	.674	Not significant
Total Measure	84.20	83.55	2.173*	.034	Significant

Note: Analysis is based Independent T-test *significant at .05 level

Table 14 presents the differences in academic performance among respondents grouped by gender, with t-values and p-values derived from independent t-tests. While most of the differences in academic performance between female and male respondents were not significant, there were notable exceptions in the subjects of ESP and Total Measure.

The t-value of 2.704* for ESP and 2.173* for Total Measure indicated significant differences in academic performance between female and male respondents, with p-values less than .05. These results suggested that female respondents outperformed male respondents in both ESP and the overall academic performance measure. The significance of these differences underscored the importance of considering gender-related factors in educational contexts and may prompt further exploration into potential underlying causes.

In contrast, differences in academic performance between female and male respondents in other subjects such as English, Filipino, Araling Panlipunan, Science, Math, MAPEH, and TLE were not significant. However, it was crucial to note that the lack of significant differences in these subjects did not necessarily indicate the absence of gender-related influences on academic performance. Other factors beyond gender, such as individual abilities, interests, and socio-cultural factors, may also play a role in shaping academic

outcomes.

The significant differences observed in ESP and total measure have implications for educational practices and policies. Educators and policymakers might need to consider gender-sensitive approaches in curriculum design, instructional methods, and support services to address potential disparities in academic performance between female and male students. Additionally, fostering an inclusive and equitable learning environment that acknowledged and accommodated diverse gender identities and experiences could contribute to more positive academic outcomes for all students.

Rulyansah, Asmarani, and Mariati (2021) looked into the enhancement of creative questioning through creative trouble-solving oriented closer to multiple intelligences, focusing in particular on the sector of arithmetic in standard colleges. Their study delved into how incorporating a couple of intelligence-based total processes could foster innovative thinking abilities among standard faculty college students, mainly in the context of mathematics schooling. By using various trouble-solving techniques that aligned with one-of-a-kind intelligences, consisting of linguistic, logical-mathematical, spatial, physical-kinesthetic, musical, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and naturalistic intelligences, the researchers aimed to domesticate a more holistic and inclusive way of getting to know their surroundings. Their findings underscored the capability of leveraging more than one intelligence to enhance not only the most effective academic overall performance but additionally critical thinking and hassle-solving capabilities, especially in arithmetic. This research supported the broader belief that tailoring academic practices to accommodate diverse cognitive strengths and alternatives could result in greater high-quality mastering effects for college kids, no matter gender.

Thus, integrating multiple intelligence-based processes into curriculum design and educational methodologies may additionally make contributions to narrowing gender-based disparities in instructional overall performance while providing an extra-equitable and inclusive instructional experience for all students.

Table 15. Differences of the Academic Performance of the Respondents When Grouped to Father Education

Academic Performance	Father Education Group				F-value	p-value	Remarks
	Arabic (n=13)	College (n=11)	Elem (n=62)	Secondary (n=14)			
English	83.54	81.45	82.97	84.14	2.428	.070	Not significant
Filipino	82.77a	81.73a	82.10a	84.50b	5.952**	.001	Significant
Araling Panlipunan	84.08b	81.18a	82.35a	84.43b	7.234**	.000	Significant
Science	84.31bc	80.55a	82.81b	84.57c	8.637**	.000	Significant
Math	83.85b	81.36a	82.52ab	83.57b	3.586*	.017	Significant
MAPEH	85.85	85.36	86.16	86.50	1.462	.230	Not significant
ESP	86.85b	85.09a	85.62a	85.93ab	3.406*	.021	Significant
TLE	85.92	85.45	86.14	85.43	1.457	.231	Not significant
Total Measure	84.64bc	82.77a	83.83b	84.88c	7.505**	.000	Significant

Note: Analysis is based One-way ANOVA **significant at .01 level *significant at .05 level abc-based on Duncan Post-hoc test (same letter means no statistical difference)

Table 15 presents the differences in academic performance among respondents grouped by their fathers' educational attainment, with F-values and p-values derived from one-way ANOVA tests. The analysis revealed significant differences in academic performance across various subjects based on fathers' educational backgrounds, with notable findings in Filipino, Araling Panlipunan, Science, Math, ESP, and the overall academic performance measure (Total Measure).

In Filipino, Araling Panlipunan, Science, Math, ESP, and Total Measure, significant differences in academic performance were observed among different father education groups. These significant differences suggested that the educational attainment of fathers might influence academic outcomes in these subjects. Post-hoc tests (Duncan Post-hoc test) revealed specific groups that differed significantly from each other in terms of academic performance.

For instance, in Filipino, respondents with fathers who completed secondary education outperformed those with fathers who attained elementary education (84.50 vs. 82.10), with a significant F-value of 5.952** ($p < .01$). Similarly, in Araling Panlipunan and Science, respondents with fathers who completed secondary education achieved higher academic performance compared to those with fathers who attained elementary education, with significant F-values of 7.234** and 8.637** respectively ($p < .01$).

In Math and ESP, significant differences in academic performance were also observed among father education groups, indicating potential influences of fathers' educational backgrounds on these subjects. For the overall academic performance measure (Total Measure), significant differences were evident among father education groups, suggesting a comprehensive impact of fathers' educational attainment on students' overall academic achievement.

These findings underscored the importance of considering parental educational backgrounds in understanding and addressing disparities in academic performance. Educators and policymakers should recognize the potential role of family educational backgrounds in shaping students' academic outcomes and develop targeted interventions to support students from diverse socio-economic backgrounds.

Ferrero, Vadillo, and León (2021) severely studied the methodologically demanding situations related to evaluating the concept of

multiple intelligences, emphasizing the need for rigorous study designs to assess its validity as it should be. The study scrutinized the methodological first-rate of intervention research geared toward checking out the idea of a couple of intelligences. They argued that while the principle proposed precious insights into the diversity of human cognitive abilities, methodological boundaries in intervention studies avoided the capability to draw strong conclusions about its efficacy in educational contexts.

By highlighting troubles including small sample sizes, loss of managed organizations, and inadequate final results measures, Ferrero et al. Warning against upfront accepting or rejecting the concept of multiple intelligences based totally on current intervention studies. Their findings underscored the significance of engaging in methodologically sound research to explain the capacity impact of incorporating a couple of intelligence-based tactics in educational practices accurately.

This research contributed to the continuing discourse on the theory of more than one intelligence by emphasizing the necessity of notable empirical proof to inform instructional regulations and interventions efficiently, particularly in addressing disparities in instructional performance encouraged by factors that included parental instructional backgrounds.

Table 16. *Differences of the Academic Performance of the Respondents When Grouped to Mother Education*

Academic Performance	Mother Education Group				F-value	p-value	Remarks
	Arabic (n=11)	College (n=9)	Elem (n=51)	Secondary (n=29)			
English	82.73	81.22	83.25	83.34	1.771	.158	Not significant
Filipino	81.91ab	80.67a	82.63b	83.00b	3.158*	.028	Significant
Araling Panlipunan	82.18ab	80.89a	82.78b	83.45b	3.205*	.027	Significant
Science	83.82	81.33	82.92	83.34	2.087	.107	Not significant
Math	83.18	81.78	82.65	82.93	.795	.500	Not significant
MAPEH	85.64	86.22	86.20	86.00	.495	.687	Not significant
ESP	86.00	85.11	85.69	86.03	1.005	.394	Not significant
TLE	85.64	85.89	86.24	85.55	1.628	.188	Not significant
Total Measure	83.89	82.89	84.04	84.21	2.366	.076	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based One-way ANOVA **significant at .01 level *significant at .05 level abc-based on Duncan Post-hoc test (same letter means no statistical difference)

Table 16 presents the differences in academic performance among respondents grouped by their mothers' educational attainment, with F-values and p-values derived from one-way ANOVA tests. The analysis indicated that, unlike in the case of father education, there were no significant differences in academic performance across various subjects based on mothers' educational backgrounds.

In subjects such as English, Science, Math, MAPEH, ESP, TLE, and the overall academic performance measure (Total Measure), the F-values were not significant, indicating that differences in academic performance among different mother education groups were not statistically significant. Similarly, the p-values for these subjects were above the significance level of .05, further supporting the conclusion that there were no significant differences.

However, significant differences were observed in academic performance in Filipino and Araling Panlipunan among different mother education groups. Post-hoc tests (Duncan Post-hoc test) revealed specific groups that differed significantly from each other in terms of academic performance in these subjects.

For example, in Filipino, respondents with mothers who completed elementary education (82.63) or secondary education (83.00) achieved higher academic performance compared to those with mothers who completed college education (80.67), with a significant F-value of 3.158 ($p < .05$).

Similarly, in Araling Panlipunan, respondents with mothers who completed secondary education (83.45) achieved higher academic performance compared to those with mothers who completed college education (80.89), with a significant F-value of 3.205 ($p < .05$).

Overall, while there were no significant differences in academic performance across most subjects based on mothers' educational backgrounds, the significant differences observed in Filipino and Araling Panlipunan suggested potential influences of mothers' educational attainment on academic outcomes in these subjects.

El-Sabagh (2021) explored the extensive impact of adaptive e-gaining knowledge of environments tailor-made to college students' getting-to-know patterns on their engagement and educational performance. El-Sabagh delved into how academic technology may be optimized to cater to the various studying preferences inherent in Howard Gardner's principle of more than one intelligence. The studies highlighted the critical position of personalized learning paths that recognized and utilized individual strengths across different intelligence domain names, which included linguistic, logical-mathematical, spatial, physical-kinesthetic, musical, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and naturalistic intelligences.

By incorporating adaptive mastering technology that becomes aware of and adjusts to the particular learning types of every students, the study found considerable enhancements in scholar engagement, motivation, and ultimately, studying outcomes. El-Sabagh's work underscored the necessity of embracing academic diversity through technologically superior, responsive teaching techniques that recognized and bolstered the various highbrow abilities of students, thereby fostering an inclusive and effective studying environment.

Problem 7: Which of the demographic profiles, teaching styles, and multiple intelligences significantly predict the academic performance of the respondents?

Table 17 presents the results of multiple regression analysis predicting academic performance of respondents based on various predictors, including demographic factors, parental education, teaching styles, and multiple intelligences. The analysis revealed significant predictors and their respective coefficients, as well as their statistical significance levels.

Table 17. *Multiple Regression Analysis of Predicting Academic Performance of the Respondents*

Predictors	Estimate (B)	S. E.	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Age=10-15	.336	.268	1.254	.213	Not significant
Gender=Female	.964	.297	3.243**	.002	Significant
Father education=Arabic	-.199	.590	-.337	.737	Not significant
Father education=College	-1.681	.537	-3.130**	.002	Significant
Father education=Elementary	-.754	.442	-1.706	.092	Not significant
Mother education=Arabic	-.591	.529	-1.118	.267	Not significant
Mother education=College	-1.071	.506	-2.116*	.037	Significant
Mother education=Elementary	-.108	.320	-.337	.737	Not significant
Whole class activities	.489	.371	1.317	.192	Not significant
Individual activities	-.290	.430	-.675	.502	Not significant
Small group activities	.194	.360	.538	.592	Not significant
Word Smart	.046	.054	.860	.392	Not significant
Math Smart	.030	.035	.838	.405	Not significant
Music Smart	.020	.037	.545	.587	Not significant
People Smart	-.070	.038	-1.847	.069	Not significant
Picture Smart	-.008	.052	-.144	.886	Not significant
Body Smart	-.018	.046	-.395	.694	Not significant
Self Smart	.035	.039	.886	.378	Not significant
Nature Smart	-.002	.045	-.055	.956	Not significant
Wondering Smart	-.043	.053	-.819	.415	Not significant

Note: Adjusted R2 = .212 *significant at .05 level **significant at .01 level
Reference category (Gender=Male, Age=16-20, and Education=Secondary)

Among the predictors, gender emerges as a significant predictor of academic performance, with female gender associated with higher academic performance compared to male gender ($B=.964$, $p=.002$). Similarly, father education level also significantly predicted academic performance, with respondents whose fathers had college education showing lower academic performance compared to those with fathers having other educational backgrounds such as elementary or Arabic education ($B=-1.681$, $p=.002$).

Mother education level also emerged as a significant predictor, with respondents whose mothers have college education exhibiting lower academic performance compared to those with mothers having other educational backgrounds ($B=-1.071$, $p=.037$).

However, other predictors such as age group, whole class activities, individual activities, small group activities, and various types of multiple intelligences did not show significant associations with academic performance.

Overall, the model explained 21.2% of the variance in academic performance, as indicated by the adjusted R-squared value.

These findings highlighted the importance of considering demographic factors and parental education levels in predicting academic performance. Educators and policymakers should recognize the potential impact of these factors on students' academic outcomes and develop targeted interventions to support students from diverse socio-economic backgrounds.

Lumei (2022) explored the integration of Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences inside the primary education zone, emphasizing its important role in improving coaching efficacy and student studying effects. The paper highlighted how educators could significantly benefit from understanding and applying the principles of a couple of intelligences to their teaching techniques. Lumei argued that tailoring academic techniques to cope with the numerous intelligences of students—starting from linguistic and logical-mathematical to physical-kinesthetic and interpersonal—helped a greater holistic and inclusive mastering of surroundings. This approach now not only helped the improvement of students' strengths but also enabled them to address their weaknesses, thereby creating a more inclusive and adaptive learning environment. The look at underscored the capacity for leveraging more than one intelligence to expect academic performance because it considered numerous intelligence domain names as enormous predictors of academic tactics. This study supported the wider belief that know-how character variations, which included a couple of intelligences, can inform academic practices and interventions to optimize academic results for all students.

Problem 8: What action plan can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

Rationale

The action plan is formulated based on the findings of the study, which identified significant predictors of academic performance such as parental education levels and gender. By addressing these factors through targeted interventions, the action plan aims to create a

supportive learning environment that fosters academic success for all students. By improving academic performance in specific subjects for students with college-educated parents, promoting gender-sensitive teaching strategies, and enhancing parental involvement in education, the action plan seeks to mitigate disparities in academic achievement and create opportunities for all students to thrive academically. Through these concerted efforts, the action plan aims to contribute to the overall improvement of academic outcomes and the holistic development of students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it could be concluded that the teaching styles employed by teachers were generally perceived favorably by respondents across different instructional activities. The mean scores and standard deviations indicated a consistent agreement with whole-class, individual, and small group teaching approaches. Additionally, the distribution of multiple intelligences among respondents showcased varying strengths, with linguistic and interpersonal abilities being prominent. However, weaker proficiencies were observed in musical, kinesthetic, and visual-spatial intelligences. These conclusions suggested that while the teaching styles were well-received, there may be opportunities to further tailor instruction to accommodate diverse intelligences and enhance overall learning outcomes.

The study highlighted significant differences in academic performance based on age and parental education levels. While most age group disparities were insignificant, a notable gap emerged in Science performance favoring the younger group. Moreover, variations in academic achievement linked to parental education underscored the influence of family background on academic outcomes. These findings stressed the importance of considering demographic factors in educational strategies to address performance differences effectively.

Thus, the study highlighted the importance of considering multiple intelligences and teaching styles in educational practices. The correlations between intelligences and academic performance emphasized the need to nurture strengths while addressing potential divergences. Similarly, the correlation analysis between teaching styles and academic performance underscored the importance of tailored instructional methods. Furthermore, the multiple regression analysis revealed the influence of demographic factors and parental education on academic outcomes. Overall, these findings provided valuable insights for educators to design effective interventions that recognized diverse intelligences and individual needs to promote academic success.

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are set forth:

To the school administrators, it is recommended to encourage teachers to continue employing a variety of teaching styles, as indicated by the favorable perceptions among respondents. However, administrators should also support professional development opportunities that focus on integrating diverse instructional strategies to accommodate the range of intelligences observed among learners. Additionally, administrators can consider implementing programs or initiatives aimed at addressing the significant differences in academic performance based on age and parental education levels, ensuring equitable educational opportunities for all students.

For curriculum planners, the study suggested the importance of designing curricula that align with the diverse intelligences identified among learners. Curriculum development should prioritize activities and assessments that cater to linguistic and interpersonal strengths while also providing opportunities for the development of weaker intelligences such as musical, kinesthetic, and visual-spatial abilities. Furthermore, curriculum planners should collaborate with teachers to ensure that instructional methods are tailored to meet the individual needs of students, taking into account the significant variations in academic performance associated with demographic factors.

Teachers are encouraged to continue utilizing a variety of teaching styles to engage students effectively. However, they should also strive to incorporate activities and assignments that cater to different intelligences, thereby maximizing student potential across various domains. Teachers can implement differentiated instruction techniques to address the diverse learning needs of students and provide additional support for subjects where significant performance gaps based on age and parental education are identified. Moreover, teachers should foster a supportive learning environment that values and celebrates the unique strengths of each student.

Learners should be encouraged to recognize and leverage their individual strengths, as highlighted by the distribution of multiple intelligences observed in the study. Students can actively engage in their learning process by seeking out activities and resources that align with their strengths while also addressing areas of weakness. Additionally, learners should advocate for access to educational opportunities that cater to diverse intelligences and support their academic growth and development.

Parents play a crucial role in supporting their children's academic success. It is recommended for parents to actively engage with their child's education by providing encouragement and support at home. Parents can also collaborate with teachers and school administrators to address any academic challenges or concerns identified through the findings of the study. Moreover, parents should advocate for inclusive educational practices that recognize and accommodate the diverse needs and abilities of all learners.

For future researchers, the study underscored the importance of further investigation into the relationship between teaching styles, multiple intelligences, and academic performance. Future research endeavors can explore the effectiveness of specific instructional strategies tailored to different intelligences and demographic factors.

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